

Antifertility Effect of *Piper betle* Linn. (stalk) in Adult Male Rats[‡]

A. CHATTERJEE*, P. ADHIKARI, J. BANERJI, D. CHOUDHURY, S. JANA and A. SEN GUPTA

Centre of Advanced Studies on Natural Products, Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science & Technology, University of Calcutta, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 30 September 1992, revised 12 April 1993, accepted 15 April 1993

The alcoholic extract of stalk of leaf of *Piper betle* Linn., was fed orally to adult male albino rats at dose level of 800–1500 mg/kg body weight per rat per day for sixty consecutive days. This resulted in cessation of spermatogenesis, degenerative changes in the seminiferous tubules, epididymis, seminal vesicles, ventral prostate and coagulating glands. Reduction in the weight and fluid content of the accessory organs was also observed. It was found that the average number of implantation sites in female rats which mated with treated males reduced with dose and duration of treatment. Similarly, the cauda epididymal sperm count and motility also decreased. Amongst all doses used, 1500 mg/kg body weight of extract was effective in bringing down the fertility rate by 100% in treated rats for sixty days. The histology of testes and morphology were also affected at this dose level. The treatment also resulted in accumulation of glycogen and cholesterol in the serum and testes and increased activities of alkaline phosphatase in serum and testes and decreased activity in acid phosphatase content. Δ^5 - β -HSD and 17β -HSD were decreased significantly in testes. These results suggested antispermatogenic and antiandrogenic effects of the alcoholic extract of the plant.

Screening for male antifertility agents from *Natural Products* requires consideration of both scientific and social factors to ensure an accurate assessment of availability, potential activity and safety. Till todate a number of compounds have been isolated from higher plants which show marked antifertility effect in males¹. However most of these potential male fertility regulating agents have one drawback or other. Most of them being irreversible or metabolically toxic. So work was taken up in our laboratory keeping these problems in view and detailed studies in this laboratory for nearly half a decade have revealed that the alcoholic crude extract of the stalk of leaves of *Piper betle* Linn.

(Piperaceae) commonly known as 'Jhal Pan' in West Bengal produced antifertility effects in both sexes of albino rats. Taking in view the necessity of a potential male antifertility drug from herbs, we have undertaken systematic work on adult male albino rats following the World Health Organization (WHO) Protocol.

Results and Discussion

Gross and microscopic changes : Changes of body-weight before and after the treatment of both *Piper betle* treated and placebo (vehicle treated) did not differ significantly (Table 1). However, weight

TABLE I—CHANGES IN BODY WEIGHT AND WEIGHT OF THE REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS OF ALBINO RATES TREATED WITH ALCOHOLIC CRUDE EXTRACT OF *P. betle* (MEAN \pm S. E.)

	Body-Weight (g)		Testes	Epidi- dymides mg/100 g	Seminal vesicles body-weight	Prostate	Coagulating gland
	Initial	Final					
Placebo	176.6 \pm 9.15	311.80 \pm 38.71	477.7* \pm 23.9 462.9* \pm 39.2	436.9 \pm 49.5	182.2 \pm 17.9	241.5 \pm 12.6	54.4 \pm 4.6
EtOH extract of stalk of leaves of <i>P. betle</i> (1500 mg/kg body- weight of rat per day for 60 days)	176.67 \pm 9.15	310.58 \pm 14.42	465.6* \pm 17.3 438.8* \pm 22.0	414.1 \pm 21.9	116.01 \pm 13.8	201.4 \pm 28.4	50.8 \pm 3.9

*Right
*Left

[‡]Younger Scientists Award (Biochemistry Section) presented to A. Sen Gupta in the 28th Annual Convention of Chemists 1991 at Calcutta.

of all the sex accessories organs, excepting coagulating glands decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$).

Testes : Administration of crude extract to rats presented a picture with successive stages of transformation of the seminiferous epithelium into spermatozoa. 30% of the tubules showed early stages of spermatogenesis upto stage 7-8. Numbers of A-spermatogonia, preleptone and pachytone and step 7-8 spermatid (Table 2) were counted in stages 7-8 of the cycles of the seminiferous tubules at the

TABLE 2-AVERAGE COUNTS OF DIFFERENT CELL TYPES IN SEMINIFEROUS TUBULES OF TESTES*

	Type A		Type B	Preleptone	Pachytone	Spermatids
	(D)	(P)				
Placebo	39.7 ± 14.2	12.0 ± 2.7	2.7 ± 1.5	12.33 ± 4.04	8.3 ± 1.5	94.3 ± 15.7
EtOH Extract of <i>Piper betle</i> (stalk) (1250 mg/kg body-weight)	30.0 ± 6.2	3.0 ± 2.7		8.0 ± 2.6	6.00 ± 1.0	27.0 ± 18.03

(D) = Dark, (P) = Pale.

*10 tubules per slide-5 slides per rat, average of 3 rats; values mean ± S.D.

dose level of 1250 and 1500 mg/kg body weight per rat per day for 60 days consecutively. These doses produced a significant decrease in the number of germs cells and spermatides compared with placebo. Sperm counts was reduced in epididymal fluid compared to placebo and most were morphologically abnormal with many heads detached from the tails. Very few sperm were motile (Table 3).

TABLE 3-TOTAL SPERM COUNT AND PERCENTAGE MOTILITY OF SPERM OF ALCOHOLIC CRUDE EXTRACT TREATED

	RATS AND PLACEBO		<i>Piper betle</i>	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
Total sperm count (million per cauda tissue)	56.6 ± 1.9	57.7 ± 1.67	31.25 ± 2.8	17.42 ± 3.7
Sperm motility (%)	59.2 ± 1.7	57.2 ± 2.1	12.19 ± 2.7	10.7 ± 2.1

Mean ± S. E.

(a) = 1250 and (b) = 1500 mg/kg body-weight/rat/day for 60 days.

TABLE 4-STUDY OF BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS*

Parameter	Placebo		<i>Piper betle</i>	
	Serum	Testes	Serum	Testes
Protein ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of tissue)		163.8 ± 2.7		122.3 ± 2.8
Alkaline 'Pase' ($\mu\text{g}/\text{h}/\text{mg}/\text{ml}$ of tissue or serum)	8.09 ± 2.0	1.97 ± 0.01	8.80 ± 2.03	1.89 ± 0.02
Acid 'Pase' ($\mu\text{g}/\text{h}/\text{mg}/\text{ml}$ of tissue or serum)	3.94 ± 0.4	1.67 ± 0.31	3.54 ± 0.5	1.78 ± 0.17
Glycogen (mg/g)		2.01 ± 0.09		1.07 ± 0.17
Cholesterol (mg/100 ml/ g of serum/tissue)	90.04 ± 0.06	7.63 ± 0.79	133.0 ± 0.3	27.9 ± 0.6
$\Delta^5\text{-}3\beta\text{-HSD}$ (units/mg protein/min)		18.03 ± 0.84		8.91 ± 2.9
$17\beta\text{-HSD}$ (units/mg protein/min)		8.9 ± 0.8		5.63 ± 0.74

mean ± S.E.

* 1500 mg/kg body-weight/rat/day for 60 consecutive days.

Biochemical events (Table 4).

Protein : Protein contents of testes of treated rats was reduced ($P < 0.02$) in comparison to vehicle treated.

Glycogen : It was reduced significantly ($P < 0.05$) in the testes of treated rats.

Cholesterol : An elevation of testicular and serum cholesterol were recorded significantly ($P < 0.03$) following treatment with curde extract of stalk of *P. betle*.

$\Delta^5\text{-}3\beta\text{-Hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase}$ and $17\beta\text{-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase}$: Reduced testicular activity in both cases were noted in crude extract of *P. betle* treated rats in comparison to placebo.

Acid and alkaline phosphatases : Mild changes were noted in both testes and serum in comparison to placebo.

The results revealed that oral administration of alcoholic crude extract of stalk of leaves of *P. betle* manifested two principal impacts on the male reproductive system of albino rats, viz. antispermatogenic and antiandrogenic effects. The antispermatogenic effect is reflected in the cessation of spermatogenesis and disintegration of sperm. Alkaline phosphatase is widely distributed in testes

and is important in the physiology of sperm². Increase in its activity is indicative of suppression of spermatogenesis and/or suppression of exchange of materials between germinal and sertoli cells³. Reduced levels of glycogen in testes indicated impaired glycolysis. So alteration in oxidative/or energy metabolism may have happened and this may be the cause of non-motility of sperm in drug-induced animals.

Oral administration of alcoholic crude extract of stalk of leaves of *P. betle* treated (1250 and 1500 mg/kg body weight/rat/day for 60 consecutive days) did not cause loss in body-weight. However, the weight of all sex organs decreased excepting coagulating glands (Table 1) and reflected antiandrogenic action of this extract.

Biochemical changes in the testes and serum are presented in the Table 3. In general, treatment of male rats with stalk of leaves of *P. betle* (alcoholic crude extract) resulted in significant changes in the levels of the biochemical parameters. The accumulation of cholesterol indicated reduced steroidogenesis by the testes of treated rats as compared to placebo. This may also be the cause of decrease in testes-weight of the treated rats. Extract manifested strong antiandrogenic effects are also supported by the decreased activities of Δ^3 -3 β -HSD and 17 β -HSD of testes. Low levels of protein in the testes after *P. betle* treatment impedes the arrest of spermatogenesis and causes inhibition of gonadotrophin and androgen output. Atrophy in androgen target organs, rarefaction in stage specific spermatogenic cells and decrease of protein contents point out that *P. betle* exhibited its antiandrogenic effects in rats. Reduced glycogen content in testes after *P. betle* treatment indicated impaired glycolysis². This might be due to alterations in oxidative and/or energy metabolism.

Oral administration to rats at different dose level strongly suggest that 1500 mg/kg of extract was most effective in causing 100% negative fertility in females after mating with treated male rats fed for 60 days.

The antiandrogenic action of this stalk of leaves of *P. betle* in itself would explain the histological changes in the seminiferous tubules because androgen is essential for most stages of spermatogenesis, meiosis in particular. It is known

that sperm production cannot proceed optimally to completion without a continuous androgen supply⁴. However, the incidence of low sperm count, presence of non-motile spermatozoa and reduction in the epididymal weight imply *P. betle* induced infertility might be the consequence of an array of factors in biochemical events in tissues and serum.

Experimental

Preparation of crude alcoholic extract of stalk of *Piper betle* Linn. and detailed of other procedure are mentioned elsewhere^{5,6}. Healthy, adult male rats of Charles Foster Strain, weighing 180–200 g (4–5 months) were used. These were maintained on standard diet and water *ad libitum* at room temperature ($25 \pm 3^\circ$; illumination 14 h). The animals were divided into experimental (drug treated) and placebo (received only the vehicle, i.e. olive oil, Bertoli, Italy).

The rats of experimental groups were fed alcoholic crude extract of stalk of leaves of *P. betle* dissolved in olive oil at different doses, i.e. 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25 and 1.5 g/kg body weight orally/day (5–10 rats per group was taken) for 60 consecutive days following the protocols of World Health Organization (WHO) MB-50⁷. The rats were weighed before and after the treatment. After 24 h of the last doses given, all rats were sacrificed by cervical dislocation. Testes, epididymis, seminal vesicles, ventral prostate and coagulating glands were dissected out and surrounding connective tissues etc. were removed and blotted free of blood and mucous. The sperm count and percentage motility from cauda epididymis were done using haemocytometer⁵. A midportion of the tissues were fixed in Bouin's fluid after recording their weights for histopathological changes. Rest of the testes were taken for estimation of protein⁸, acid and alkaline phosphatases⁹, glycogen¹⁰, cholesterol¹¹ and Δ^5 -3 β -hydroxysteroiddehydrogenase (HSD) 17 β -hydroxysteroiddehydrogenase¹². Serum analyses were done for both acid and alkaline phosphatase and cholesterol. Stages of spermatogenesis was noted according to Leblond and Clemont¹³. Student 't' test was applied for comparing means.

References

1. N. R. FANSWORTH, S. A. BINGEL, D. D. SOEJARTO, ROB WIJESEKERO and S. J. PEREA, 'Symposium on Recent

- Advances in Fertility Regulation', Beijing, 1980, pp. 330-364; S. D. SETH, M. JOHRI and K. R. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Pharmacol.*, 1982, **14**, 207; S. AGARWAL, S. CHAUHAN and R. MATHUR, *Andrologia*, 1986, **18**, 125; GU, ZHI PING Y. GUANG, SANG, W. WANG, Y. X. WAY, X. J. ZHAO, D. Z. CHENG, L. J. GE and X. H. LIU, 'The Proceedings of a Symposium on Advances in Fertility Regulation in the Male', Nanjing, China, 1984, p. 42; M. G. WANG, M. Z. GUAN and H. LEI, 'The Proceedings of a Symposium on Advances in Fertility Regulation in the Male', Nanjing, China, 1984, p. 49; V. P. DIXIT and S. JOSHI, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1982, **20**, 534; S. CHATTOPADHYA, U. CHATTOPADHYA, P. P. MATHUR, K. S. SAINI and S. GHOSAL, *Planta Medica*, 1983, **49**, 252.
2. T. MANN, "Biochemistry of the Semen and of the Male Reproductive Tract", Maltheren, London, 1964, p 54.
 3. N. NAIR, M. S. EDWARDS, R. S. BEDWALL and R. S. MATHUR, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1987, **25**, 651.
 4. H. MOHRI, D. A. E. SUTUR, P. D. E. BROWN-WOEDMAN, I. G. WHITE and P. D. RIDLEY, *Nature*, 1978, **255**, 75; T. MANN and C. L. MANN *Biochem. Soc. Symp.*, 1951, **7**, 11; L. J. RODRIGUEZE-RIGAUE, D. B. WEISS, Z. ZUCKMAN, H. E. GROTTJAN, K. D. SMITH and E. STEINBERGER, *J. Fertil. Steril.*, 1969, **30**, 577; D. E. BROOKS, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1981, **61**, 515; H. D. M. MOORE and J. M. BEDFORD, *Anat. Rec.*, 1979, **193**, 313.
 5. P. ADHIKARI, J. BANERJI, D. CHOWDHURI, A. K. DAS, C. C. DEB, S. R. MUKHERJEE and A. CHATTERJEE, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1989, **27**, 868.
 6. P. ADHIKARI, J. BANERJI, D. CHOWDHURY, A. K. DAS, C. C. DEB, S. R. MUKHERJEE and A. CHATTERJEE, *Indian J. Pharmacol.*, 1990, **22**, 145.
 7. WHO-MB-50, AP/9113E (Geneva), 1983.
 8. O. H. LOWRY, M. T. ROSEBROUGH, R. J. FARR and R. J. ROHDATT, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1981, **193**, 265.
 9. O. A. BESSAY, O. H. LOWRY and M. J. BROCK, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1950, **164**, 321.
 10. W. V. CARROL, R. W. LONGLY and J. H. ROE, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1956, **220**, 583.
 11. I. MACINTYRE and M. RALSTON, *Biochem. J.*, 1954, **56**, 53.
 12. P. TALALAY, "Methods in Enzymology", Academic, New York, 1962, Vol. 5, p. 512.
 13. C. P. LEBALOND and Y. DERMUT, *Ann. New York Acad. Sci.*, 1952, **55**, 548.